

OMPLICATION OF VAMANA AND THEIR MANAGEMENT WITH AYURVEDA AND MODERN APPROACHES: A REVIEW**Dr. Chandravijay Radhakishan Bhoyare^{*1}, Dr. Vijay Ganeshrao Kawale², Dr. Sudhir Kisanrao Bhujbale³**^{*1}Professor & HOD, Panchakarma Department, Dr. Vandanatai Dhone Gramin Ayurved Mahavidyalaya, Patur, Maharashtra, India.²Assistant Professor, Department of Panchakarma, Dr. VJD Gramin Ayurved Mahavidyalaya Patur, Akola, Maharashtra, India.³Associate Professor, Dept. of Panchakarma, Late Shrimati Vandanatai Jagannathrao Dhone Gramin Ayurved Mahavidyalaya, Patur, Dist. Akola, Maharashtra, India.***Corresponding Author: Dr. Chandravijay Radhakishan Bhoyare**Professor & HOD, Panchakarma Department, Dr. Vandanatai Dhone Gramin Ayurved Mahavidyalaya, Patur, Maharashtra, India. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17284516>

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ABSTRACT

Vamana, is one of the *Panchakarma* therapies in Ayurveda, is intended to remove excessive *Kapha Dosha* from the body. Excessive *Kapha* can lead to conditions such as cough and cold, while mild excess can be managed through oral medication. Severe aggravation or dislodgment of *Kapha* at its site requires therapeutic emesis. *Vamana* helps to expel *Kapha* primarily through the oral root. The process involves moving *Kapha* from the peripheral tissues and organs into the stomach, where it is subsequently vomited out. Complications may also develop from conducting *Vamana* therapy improperly, either in *Atiyoga* and/or *Ayoga*. After *Vamana*, the patient should refrain from any activities that might disturb the recovery phase, to include loud talking, eating large amounts, long sitting, long walks, moods of anger and grief or extremes of external environmental factors such as sun, dew, or pungent wind. After *Vamana*, *Agni* is weak, therefore it is essential to build normalized digestibility back to its original state. This article described complication of *Vamana* and their management through Ayurveda and modern approaches.

KEYWORDS: *Ayurveda*, *Vamana*, *Panchakarma*, *Atiyoga*, *Ayoga*.**INTRODUCTION**

Panchakarma is a key treatment in Ayurveda whose objective is the removal of vitiated *Doshas* from the body. Among the main *Panchakarma* procedures, *Vamana* is one of the main *Samshodhana* therapies used to remove excess *Doshas*. *Vamana* is a clinical detoxification therapeutic procedure, within the *Panchakarma* framework, aimed at removing *Kapha dosha* from the body through the oral route.^[1,3]

If the *Vamana* process is not properly supervised, there could be complications. The complication we most often see is gastrointestinal bleeding in people who have gastric or peptic ulcers, or gastroesophageal reflux disease (GERD). In this situation, the procedure needs to be stopped immediately, and need to give the patient *Stambhana* drugs like *Sootashekhara Rasa*, *Mayurapiccha Bhasma* and *Kamadugha Rasa*, etc.^[3,5]

Major Complications of *Vamana* and their Management

Vamana dravya used as a treatment in Ayurveda can lead

to complications if not administered properly, or if the patient was not properly prepared prior to the treatment. These complications are generally categorized as *Atiyoga* and *Ayoga*. With *Atiyoga* complications, the patient may experience excessively vomiting, hematemesis due to the expulsion of blood and bile, hypotension from fluid and electrolyte loss, and profound weakness and cramps as well as transient symptoms of headache and dizziness. This is in contrast to *Ayoga* complications, when the emetic drug does not elicit an adequate emetic response; the patient will experience nausea, discomfort in the abdomen, flatulence and delayed purging which in turn may limit the efficacy of future treatments like *Virechana*. Therefore, careful and thorough preparation, proper administration and ongoing monitoring are really required for patient safety and good outcomes with Ayurvedic treatment.^[5,7]

Common complication is fainting generally from excessive fluid loss. In this case, lay the patient supine, elevate the foot end and lay the head end slightly down, followed by sprinkling cold water on the face. The

patient should regain consciousness rapidly; as soon as they do, you will administer intravenous fluids, such as Normal Saline, DNS, or Ringer's Lactate, to help replace lost fluids and help resolve electrolyte imbalance. Therefore it is advisable to have IV sets and fluids prepared ahead of time for emergency use.

Minor complications that may happen with *Vamana* could include abdominal cramps or skin rashes. In this case, hot packs, or *Pata Sweda*, can be administered over the abdominal region. If the *Vamana* exceeds 45 minutes of time, the emetic drugs may have a tendency to digest, resulting in *Adhopravrutti*. In this situation one should

not use *Stambhana*, or it will worsen the episode.

Excessive administration can cause abdominal bloating/distension or cutting type pain, excessive salivation, anxiety or jitteriness, rigidity, dislocation of viscera, stiffness, fatigue, blood-streaked or foamy emesis, dry throat, burning or heating sensation in the body, dizziness, or in related extreme cases, excessive blood loss can be life threatening. Excessive emesis can also spark *Vata* disorder complications in emesis, troublesome ability of verbal tasks, foam with emesis, etc. **Table 1** depicted some complications of few common *Vamana Dravyas* if used improperly.^[6,8]

Table 1: Complications of common *Vamana Dravyas* (in case of *Atiyoga / Ayoga*).

<i>Vamana Dravya</i>	Common Complications
<i>Madanaphala</i>	Excessive vomiting, hypotension, headache and dehydration, etc.
<i>Koshataki</i>	Weak emesis (<i>Ayoga</i>); abdominal discomfort and bloating
<i>Kutaja</i>	Nausea and incomplete expulsion of <i>Kapha</i>
<i>Jimutaka</i>	Excessive vomiting, muscle cramps, fatigue and dizziness
<i>Ikshvaku</i>	Nausea, hypotension and abdominal discomfort, etc.

Precaution and Care during *Vamana* Process

Following the successful performance of *Vamana*, the patient's hands, feet, and face should be washed with warm water so that comfort can be restored with some consolation. Herbal smoking is suggested just after the process has been completed, and then the patient will be left to rest in a wind-free room on a calm bed in a shelter of a protected space. If there has been inadequate emesis

during the process, additional doses of *Madana Phala Kashaya* or *Yashtimadhu Phanta* will be administered, which will result in emesis. If this is unsuccessful, the client will be advised to use the *Samsarjana Krama* and plan for *Vamana* again a few days later. **Figure 1** depicted major approaches which should be followed to avoid complications of *Vamana* therapy.^[7,9]

Figure 1: Approaches of *Vamana* therapy to avoid complications.

After *Vamana*, the patient is required to avoid activities that can interfere with the recovery process, including talking loudly, overeating, prolonged sitting, long-distance walking, anger and grief or extremes of external environmental factors such as sun, dew or pungent wind. Additionally, the patient need to avoid travel, sexual activity, staying up at night, sleeping during the day and/or suppressing or forcing the natural body's urges. Dietary indiscretion, such as eating foods with opposite qualities, wrong combinations, foods not digestible, dietary monotony of one flavor, not following nutrient

dense eating pattern, eating heavy meals, and eating of food irregularly are in general to be avoided and can affect future health.

Dietary Regimen

Following *Vamana*, the digestive fire has been weakened, and thus it is important to gradually regain normal digestibility. This is done through a process called *Samsarjana Krama*. Following the procedure, or sometime the next day, the patient bathes in tepid water and begins with some thin warm rice gruel given over

the first three meal-times, then according to how reasonably possible they can digest further meals. For the fourth meal, give a slightly thicker gruel (*Vilepi*) made with rice, either plain or with a small amount of ghee/salt added, and then warm water afterwards. This will continue for the fifth and sixth meals. With the seventh meal, well-cooked porridge and thin green gram soup can be served; the soup should contain a small amount of ghee and rock salt.^[8,10]

CONCLUSION

Vamana is a primary *Panchakarma* therapy that effectively removes excessive *Kapha Dosha* from the body with this unique bio-cleansing procedure. The well-defined process involves preparatory, main, and post-care stages with multiple benefits for patients, including alleviation of diseases, improved digestion and metabolism, increased immunity, mental clarity, as well as a general state of rejuvenation. Although *Vamana* provides considerable therapeutic effects, it is critical to monitor the procedure to prevent and manage complications; gastrointestinal bleeding or fainting, or abdominal cramps, etc. Post-procedure care, such as activity regulation and diet as it's laid out in *Samsarjana Krama*, is equally relevant for restoring digestive strength and ensuring a safe recovery. When implemented correctly in accordance with classical guidelines, and modified appropriately for the modern clinical environment, *Vamana* can be a highly pertinent and useful Ayurvedic therapy for health, longevity, and prevention of disease.

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